

Texas FFA Entomology

Insect Identification Guide
2022–2026

Lillian Prescott and Jill Forrest

Revised and edited by Jennifer C. Girón

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**NATURAL SCIENCE
RESEARCH LABORATORY**

TEXAS TECH
Office of the Provost
Outreach & Engagement

**DAVIS COLLEGE OF
AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES
& NATURAL RESOURCES**

TEXAS TECH

Introduction

These fact sheets were created with students in mind and as a way for Texas FFA Entomology coaches to have a centralized source of information for all the organisms on the identification list. Both authors have previously competed on Texas FFA Entomology teams and are organizers of Areas I and II and State competitions.

Each slide contains information relevant to the identification portion of the Entomology CDE, including common name, number on the ID list, MOUTHPARTSs, metamorphosis, and significance, as indicated in the Texas FFA Official Entomology Characteristic List. Other useful information such as distinctive characteristics for ID and fun facts have also been included.

Each insect order is color coded to separate them into sections, and the organisms within each order are sorted alphabetically. Images were obtained through iNaturalist, Google Photos CC, Pexels, Pixabay, iStock, and personal images. Information for these fact sheets was gathered from many sources, both through books and online. All information was referenced across multiple sources to ensure fact sheets are current and accurate.

Disclaimer

These fact sheets are related to the Official Texas FFA ID List for Entomology 2022–2026. They reflect information for order, metamorphosis, mouthparts, and significance to humans following the Texas FFA Official Entomology Characteristic List. Since that list was created, there have been changes to the classification of certain organisms that are not reflected in these sheets. Additionally, diverse insect groups are restricted to narrow categories following what is provided in that list. We are working to fix any errors that may be present on the current list to be corrected in the upcoming 2027–2031 list.

Images in these sheets are meant to show diversity and for groups with multiple species they may include species not recorded from Texas or the United States.

Conventions

- sp. means one species; spp. means more than one species.
- The symbol ~ means approximately.
- Two asterisks (**) indicates larval or nymph forms

Blattodea

01

An Overview of the order Blattodea

Blattodea contains cockroaches and termites. All insects in this order have **chewing** mouthparts, **hemimetabolous** development, and are decomposers, with some species considered as **pests**.

Insects in this order share social habits and similar gut microbiomes.

The name Blattodea comes from “blatta”, the Greek word for cockroach.

*Questions 98 and 146 involve this order.

American Cockroach

#001

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- They can cause infestations, spread disease, ruin clothing and wallpaper, contaminate food, and even cause asthma.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Blattidae: *Periplaneta americana*

SIZE: 1.4–2 in.

FOOD: Opportunistic omnivores- they will eat anything.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: reddish-brown in color with a yellow band that outlines the area behind their head. Both males and females have wings.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Despite the name, the American cockroach isn't native to America at all- they were introduced from Africa.

German Cockroach

#056

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- they can cause infestations, spread disease, ruin clothing and wallpaper, contaminate food, and even cause asthma.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Ectobiidae: *Blattella germanica*

SIZE: 1/2–5/8 in.

FOOD: Opportunistic omnivores- they will eat anything.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: monomorphic with a flattened head, oval shape, spiny legs, long antennae. Sexually dimorphic with males having a thin and slender body, posteriorly tapered abdomen, visible terminal segments of the abdomen and do not have wings.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Females will carry and protect their oothecae (egg cases) for as long as a month, only dropping them just before they hatch.

*Question 47 involves this insect.

Oriental Cockroach

#095

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- infestations can lead to transmission of pathogens and foul odors.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Blattidae: *Blatta orientalis*

SIZE: ~ 1 in.

FOOD: Decaying plant and animal matter.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: dark brown to black, males have wings covering $\frac{3}{4}$ of their body, females have very short (rudimentary) wings. The inner wing folds like a fan and is membranous. The outer part of the wing is narrow, leathery, and thick.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Though they have wings, they are unable to fly.

Termites

#137

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- they can cause serious damage to wooden structures.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Isoptera

SIZE: ¼–½ in.

FOOD: Plant materials and structures made of plants (wood).

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Soft, straight bodies; straight antennae; often large heads. Reproductive or swarmer termites possess wings that are the same length.

Over 3,000 spp. worldwide, 45 spp. in North America, 5 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Worker termites of some species are blind.

Coleoptera

02

An Overview of the order Coleoptera

Coleoptera contains the beetles. All insects in this order have **chewing** mouthparts and **holometabolous** development.

Insects in this order share hardened forewings known as elytra. There are over 400,000 species of beetles described worldwide. It is the largest group of organisms.

The name Coleoptera comes from the Greek word “koleos” meaning sheath, and “ptera” meaning wing.

*Questions 6, 10, 18, 36, 223, and 237 involve this order.

Blister Beetles

#016

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Some species are considered pests. Adults can cause crop damage. They contain a toxin, cantharidin, that causes skin irritation and can injure or kill livestock if ingested.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Meloidae

SIZE: 0.1–0.8 in.

FOOD: Larva eat grasshopper eggs, adults eat flowers, fruit, and grasshoppers.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: narrow bodies, broad heads, with neck, antennae are ~ 1/3 length of their entire bodies. The front wings are soft and flexible.

7,500 spp. worldwide, 400 spp. in North America, ~100 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Blister beetles are often seen on flowers during the daytime. Some species can serve as pollinators.

*Question 54 involves these insects.

Boll Weevil

#018

MOUThPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- they cause severe damage to cotton crops.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Curculionidae: *Anthonomus grandis*

SIZE: ¼ in.

FOOD: Cotton plants and related vegetation.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: color varies with age starting as a neutral blue/black/gray/tan and maturing into a dark red-brown or mahogany; double-toothed spur on the inner surface of each front leg.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Boll weevils get their name from where they lay their eggs- in cotton bolls.

*Questions 53 and 243 involve this insect.

Carrion Beetles

#027

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- Their diet of decaying animals helps keep their habitat clean and cycle nutrients into the soil.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Staphylinidae, Silphinae

SIZE: 1–1.4 in.

FOOD: Decaying animals.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: flattened, usually black with markings of red/orange/yellow. The elytra have a distinctive shape, wider toward the end of the body and narrower toward the front.

138 spp. worldwide, 30 spp. in North America, 14 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Some species of carrion beetles live in beehives. Parents care for their larvae.

Cigarette Beetle

#032

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- They feed on a variety of stored household food items and cause infestations.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Ptinidae: *Lasioderma serricorne*

SIZE: 1/8 in.

FOOD: Dry stored food products.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: reddish brown, rounded oval shape, head is often concealed by the pronotum when viewed from above.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Adults live 2–4 weeks- females lay up to 100 eggs, and eggs hatch in 6–10 days.

Click Beetles

#033

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable- Their larvae (wireworms) can cause crop damage. As adults, they eat pest species and help with nutrient cycling.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Elateridae

SIZE: 1–2.5 in.

FOOD: Flower parts and soft-bodied insects such as aphids. Larvae are mostly predators on small soil animals but may also eat roots and seeds.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: long skinny beetles with grooves running down their elytra. The front of their heads and the back end of elytra are rounded.

9,300 spp. worldwide, 965 spp. in North America, 170 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Click beetles can jump by snapping a spinelike structure into a groove on their prosternum. They use this to turn themselves around when they are upside down.

Colorado Potato Beetle

#034

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- they cause damage to the leaves of garden plants.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Chrysomelidae: *Leptinotarsa decemlineata*

SIZE: 3/8 in.

FOOD: Solanaceous plants and weeds.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Yellow and black stripes, 10 black lines run along the length of the elytra, convex.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Their life cycle lasts only 5–8 weeks per generation.

Darkling Beetles

#040

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable- larvae are an important food source for reptiles and birds. Some can be a pest of dry stored food products and may cause damage to plants.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Tenebrionidae

SIZE: .1/8–1.5 in.

FOOD: Fresh and decaying vegetation.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: moniliform antennae, notched eyes, first abdominal ventrite not divided by the metacoxae.

20,000 spp. worldwide, 1,200 spp. in North America, 319 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Some species can release a foul-smelling liquid in self defense. The larvae of *Tenebrio molitor*, the yellow mealworm beetle, are sold as food for pet birds, reptiles, amphibians, and some fish.

Dermestid Beetles

#043

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- They feed on stored food and natural fibers. They can cause extensive damage to taxidermy and other preserved dry specimens.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Dermestidae

SIZE: 1/16–1/2 in.

FOOD: dried meat- larvae prefer leathers.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Body is generally oval with hairy or scaly elytra.

500 spp. worldwide, 123 spp. in North America, ~ 50 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Dermestids can be helpful in museum and collection settings for cleaning animal bones.

*Question 80 involves these insects.

Elm Leaf Beetles

#048

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- they cause damage to elm leaves. They may occasionally be nuisance home invaders but won't cause damage in the home.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Chrysomelidae: *Xanthogaleruca luteola*

SIZE: ~¼ in.

FOOD: Elm leaves.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Oval shaped, yellow to olive green, black stripe along each elytra, 3–4 dark spots on pronotum

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Their eggs are lemon shaped and colored, and laid in groups of 25 or more on the underside of leaves.

Fireflies

#051

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- larvae feed on snails, slugs, and soft bodied pest insects; some adults are pollinators.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Lampyridae

SIZE: 1/4–3/4 in.

FOOD: Soft bodied invertebrates like snails, slugs, worms, and larvae.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Soft bodied, flat oval shaped bodies, dark wings.

Over 2,400 spp. worldwide, over 270 spp. in North America, 45 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Fireflies use their lights to communicate with each other. Even the eggs of some species glow!

*Question 223 involves these insects.

Flea beetles

#053

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- they can transmit diseases between plants and cause extensive leaf damage.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Chrysomelidae: Alticini

SIZE: 1/16–1/8 in.

FOOD: Plant material.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: They have enlarged back femora for jumping.

6,000 spp. worldwide, ~440 spp. in North America, ~117 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Flea beetles are strong fliers.

Ground Beetles

#060

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Carabidae

SIZE: 1/8–1 in.

FOOD: Most species eat soft and hard bodied arthropods; some eat leaf tissue and seeds.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Elytra with longitudinal grooves and may be fused along the midline. First abdominal ventrite divided by the metacoxae. Many species have reduced or absent hind wings.

40,000 spp. worldwide, ~2,000 spp. in North America, 690 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: One group of ground beetles, the bombardiers, shoot out boiling hot toxins from their abdomen as self defense.

*Question 27 involves these insects.

Ironclad Beetles

#071

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Tenebrionidae: Zopherinae

SIZE: ½ –1 ¼ in.

FOOD: Mostly fresh and rotting plant material and fungi.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Robust legs, thick and densely layered interlocking elytra.

1,700 spp. worldwide, 110 spp. in North America, ~19 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They play dead as a defense mechanism. Some species can live up to 8 years.

Ladybird Beetles

#076

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- Feed on aphids and other garden pests.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Coccinellidae

SIZE: 0.3–0.4 in.

FOOD: Insects and insect eggs.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Round to oval and dome-shaped.

6,000 spp. worldwide, 500 spp. in North America, 136 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Ladybird beetles hibernate in large groups.

Ladybird Beetle Larva**

#077

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- Feed on aphids and other garden pests.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Coccinellidae

SIZE: up to 1/3 in.

FOOD: Insects and insect eggs.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Spiny body with prominent legs and elongated slightly pointed rear.

6,000 spp. worldwide, 500 spp. in North America, 136 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Some say ladybird beetle larvae resemble tiny alligators.

Longhorned Beetles

#081

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- larvae feed on the wood of trees and decaying wood.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Cerambycidae

SIZE: $\frac{3}{4}$ – 1 $\frac{1}{2}$ in.

FOOD: Pollen, nectar, fruit, trees.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Antennae as long or longer than the body, typically a long and cylindrical body.

35,000 spp. worldwide, ~ 1,000 spp. in North America, over 400 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They can make squeaking sounds by rubbing their head against their thorax.

Metallic Woodboring Beetles

#086

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- Larvae feed on the wood of trees (usually ones already in poor health), adults feed on leaves.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Buprestidae

SIZE: 0.3–2.5 in.

FOOD: wood of trees and shrubs as larvae; plant foliage, nectar, and wood as adults.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Body long, narrow, and flat with a tapering abdomen. Shiny, metallic body with structural color rather than pigment.

15,000 spp. worldwide, 700 spp. in North America, 318 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Due to their opulent appearance, they were used as living jewelry in the Victorian age.

Predaceous Diving Beetles

#100

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- Important in aquatic food chains, larvae are beneficial for mosquito control.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Dytiscidae

SIZE: 1/16–1 3/4 in.

FOOD: Mosquito larvae as larvae; scavengers and eating small aquatic animals as adults.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Filiform antennae, sickle-shaped mandibles, and long flattened fringed back legs.

Over 4,000 spp. worldwide, over 550 spp. in North America, 70+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Their family name, Dytiscidae, means "able to dive" in Greek.

*Question 18 involves these insects.

Red Flour beetle

#103

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- Can damage and contaminate food supplies. Eating contaminated food can lead to food poisoning and allergic reactions.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Tenebrionidae: *Tribolium castaneum*

SIZE: ~4 mm.

FOOD: Stored grain products.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: shiny reddish-brown body, flattened and oval shaped, antennae abruptly end in a large 3-antennomere club.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Females can lay 200–450 eggs in her lifetime over 1–3 years. Eggs hatch in 5–12 days and depending on the weather the larva takes 30–120 days to mature.

Rice Weevil

#106

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- they are a pest of stored grain products.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Curculionidae: *Sitophilus oryzae*

SIZE: ~ 1/8 in.

FOOD: Grains, cotton, fruits.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: dull reddish-brown to black with round or irregularly shaped pits on the thorax and four light reddish or yellowish spots on the elytra.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Females can lay 300–400 eggs. She will drill a hole in a grain kernel and deposit her egg, typically only laying one egg per kernel.

Rove Beetles

#108

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- they can help reduce pest populations in farms and gardens.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Staphylinidae

SIZE: 1/16 – 1 ¼ in.

FOOD: Soft bodied insects and dead animals.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Slender bodies typically with elongated abdomens and reduced elytra.

Over 66,000 spp. worldwide, ~ 4,000 spp. in North America, 130+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Rove beetles make up one of the largest beetle families in North America.

Sawtoothed Grain Beetle

#109

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- They can contaminate food and damage stored products.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Silvanidae: *Oryzaephilus surinamensis*

SIZE: ¼ in.

FOOD: Stored grains and grain products.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Brown flattened body, saw-toothed projections on the side of the prothorax.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Though they have well-developed wings, there are no records of these insects flying.

Scarab Beetles

#111

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable- Some species are turf and garden pests; other species are important in decomposition and nitrogen and nutrient cycling.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Scarabaeidae

SIZE: 1/32–4 ½ in.

FOOD: Dung and dead/decomposing plants and animals.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Stout-bodied, clubbed antennae composed of plates called lamellae that can be compressed into a ball or fanned out.

Over 35,000 spp. worldwide, 1,300 spp. in North America, 471 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Scarabs are one of the strongest insects in the world.

Soldier Beetles

#118

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- they help control pest populations and act as pollinators.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Cantharidae

SIZE: 5–15 mm.

FOOD: Insect eggs and soft-bodied insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: elongate, head commonly bent downward, moniliform antennae of 11 antennomeres, pronotum usually wider than head and wider than long.

3,500 spp. worldwide, 500 spp. in North America, 19 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: As self defense, they secrete defensive chemical compounds to make themselves less appealing to predators.

Spotted Cucumber Beetle

#123

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- Adults feed on leaves and larvae feed on roots, causing crop damage.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Chrysomelidae: *Diabrotica undecimpunctata*

SIZE: ~ ¼ in.

FOOD: Seedlings, flower petals, leaves, and fruit.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Yellow to green with 12 black spots on the elytra, head and legs are black with filiform black antennae.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Spotted cucumber beetles aren't picky eaters- they feed on over 200 plant species across 50 families.

Stag Beetles

#126

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable- adults may feed on leaves but not enough to be considered pests.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Lucanidae

SIZE: 1 ½– 3 in.

FOOD: Adults don't eat solid food, but they consume sweet fluids like sap and decomposing fruit.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Males often have prominent mandibles.

1,200 spp. worldwide, 24 spp. in North America, 4 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Stag beetles are found all throughout the world, excluding Australia and Antarctica.

Sweet Potato Weevil

#133

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- feed on and cause damage to tubers

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Brentidae: *Cylas formicarius*

SIZE: ¼ – 3/8 in.

FOOD: Plants in the Convolvulaceae family.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Prothorax and legs are red, but the rest of the body is blue-black, snout is slightly curved, slightly ant-like appearance.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They are the most serious sweet potato pest in the world.

Tiger Beetles

#139

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- They feed on other insects, helping to control pest populations

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Carabidae: Cicindelinae

SIZE: ~ ½ in.

FOOD: Other small invertebrates.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Large bulging eyes, long slender legs, large curved mandibles.

2,600 spp. worldwide, 117 spp. in North America, 47 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They can run so fast that their eyes can't keep up, rendering them temporarily blind- this is why they only run for short bursts.

Tumbling Flower Beetles

#146

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable- They can cause chewing damage to flowers, but they are beneficial as pollinators.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Mordellidae

SIZE: 0.1–0.3 in.

FOOD: Nectar and pollen.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Thin antennae, abdomen protrudes to a point extending beyond the elytra.

~ 1,500 spp. worldwide, 200 spp. in North America, over 30 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: When threatened these beetles can kick their legs, causing them to bounce and tumble unpredictably, confusing predators.

Whirligig Beetles

#153

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- can help improve water quality by feeding on dead and dying insects.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Gyrinidae

SIZE: 1/8–1 1/2 in.

FOOD: Insects that fall into the water.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Oval streamlined body; forelegs are long and slender; middle and hind legs are short, flattened and fold tightly under the body; legs of meso- and metathorax are modified into flat paddles.

700 spp. worldwide, ~50 spp. in North America, 8+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They have split eyes, with the dorsal area to see above the water the ventral area to see below the water.

*Question 180 involves these insects.

White Grub**

#154

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- destructive to turfgrass

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Scarabaeidae

SIZE: 3/8–2 in.

FOOD: Roots of grasses.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: C-shaped, creamy-white body with reddish-brown head and well-developed legs.

Over 3,500 spp. worldwide, 1,300 spp. in North America, 471 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Many complete development in a year, but the June Beetle has a 3-year life cycle.

Collembola

03

An Overview of the order Collembola

Collembola contains springtails. All insects in this order have **chewing** mouthparts and **ametabolous** development.

Springtails share a tail like organ underneath their abdomen, known as a furcula, that they use to “spring” themselves into the air.

Collembola comes from the greek words “coll” meaning glue, and “embol” meaning wedge, referring to the structure on the first abdominal segment that bears a colophore, first thought to be an adhesive organ.

*Question 108 involves this order.

Springtail

#124

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable-they fertilize the soil by eating bacteria, fungi, lichens, algae, and decaying vegetation. They can make small holes in leaves on young plants.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Collembola

SIZE: 1/64–1/4 in.

FOOD: Decaying organic materials, molds, mildews.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Wingless, with forked structure under abdomen.

6,000 spp. worldwide, ~700 spp. in North America, 70+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They can spring up to 8 in. in the air- the equivalent of a human jumping up to a 10-story building.

Dermaptera

04

An Overview of the order Dermaptera

Dermaptera contains earwigs. All insects in this order have **chewing** mouthparts and **hemimetabolous** development.

Insects in this order share an abdomen that ends in long, unsegmented cerci.

Dermaptera comes from the Greek words "derma" meaning skin, and "ptera" meaning wing, referring to the skin-like appearance of their forewings.

*Question 99 involves this order.

Earwigs

#047

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- they eat small pest species and help the breakdown of organic materials.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Dermaptera

SIZE: ¼–2 in.

FOOD: Opportunistic feeders- they will eat just about anything.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Cerci (pair of forceps-like pinchers on their abdomen), male cerci more curved than females; filiform antennae with 10 antennomeres.

~ 2,000 spp. worldwide, ~20 spp. in North America, ~10 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: While most insects don't give parental care, earwig mothers guard their eggs and care for their babies.

*Question 99 involves these insects.

Diptera

05

An Overview of the order Diptera

Diptera contains flies, mosquitos, and midges. All insects in this order have **holometabolous** development.

Insects in this order only have one pair of wings, with the second pair modified into halteres, which help maintain balance in flight.

Diptera comes from the Greek words “di” meaning two, and “ptera” meaning wing, referring to their two wings (other insects have four).

*Questions 38, 40, 123, and 248 involve this order.

Bee Flies

#010

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- bee flies are great pollinators.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Bombyliidae

SIZE: 1/32–7/8 in.

FOOD: Nectar and pollen.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Two wings, large eyes, skinny long legs, very short antennae, many have hairy bodies, wings often with dark patches.

5,000 spp. worldwide, 800 spp. in North America, 112+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They are very strong fliers and can hover in midair.

Blow Flies

#017

MOUTHPARTS: Sponging

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- feed on dead animals and garbage and have potential to spread disease. Some species are parasitic. Important decomposers.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Calliphoridae

SIZE: 0.3–0.4 in.

FOOD: Decaying meat.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Two wings, short antennae, large compound eyes, often shiny and metallic with hairlike bristles.

~ 1,900 spp. worldwide, 93 spp. in North America, 23+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Females can lay 2,000 eggs in their short 10–25-day life cycle.

Cattle Grub**

#028

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- major economic pest in the cattle industry. Causes decreased weight and tissue damage.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Oestridae: *Hypoderma* spp.

SIZE: 5/8 in.

FOOD: Live cattle flesh.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: No legs, white to brownish color, body with rings of strong bristles.

2 spp. worldwide, 2 spp. in North America, 2 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Adults are called Warble flies or "heel flies" because they cause cattle to kick themselves.

Crane Flies

#036

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable- larvae feed on decaying organic matter and help with the decomposition cycle, but some feed on roots and cause damage to turf grass.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Tipulidae

SIZE: $\frac{3}{4}$ in. bodies and 4 in. legs.

FOOD: Larvae eat decaying organic matter, plant roots, and insects. Adults rarely eat but may feed on nectar.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Long, thin body; thin smoky wings and extremely long legs; most have visible halteres.

15,500 spp. worldwide, ~ 1,500 spp. in North America, 70+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Crane flies spend 95% percent of their life in their larval stage.

Deer Flies

#041

MOUTHPARTS: Cutting-sponging

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- sucks blood of horses, cattle, and humans; can transmit disease (tularemia).

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Tabanidae: Chrysopsinae
Chrysops spp.

SIZE: ¼ - 1/3 in.

FOOD: Females drink blood, males eat pollen and nectar.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Yellow to black, stripes on abdomen, mottled wings with dark patches.

250 spp. worldwide, 120 spp. in North America, 33 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Females can lay between 100 and 800 eggs.

Deer Keds

#042

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- they repeatedly feed on their host's blood.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Hippoboscidae: *Lipoptena cervi*

SIZE: ~ ¼ in.

FOOD: Blood.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Appear somewhat tick-like; brown, flattened body; have wings upon emergence but lose wings when they land on a host.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They can live for at least a year on their hosts.

Flesh Flies

#054

MOUTHPARTS: Sponging

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- can infest open wounds; food contaminated by larvae can cause intestinal infection if consumed.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Sarcophagidae

SIZE: 3/8–1/2 in.

FOOD: Fluids from animal bodies, nectar, sweet foods, animal waste, and other organic substances.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Checkerboard pattern on abdomen with three black stripes on thorax.

2,000 spp. worldwide, 327 spp. in North America, 12+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: The name flesh fly comes from the fact that some species will lay their eggs in open wounds.

Horn Flies

#065

MOUTHPARTS: Cutting-lapping

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- economic pest in the cattle industry. Extensive feeding on cattle damages hide, and stress caused by infestation can lower milk production and lead to lowered grazing time and decreased weight.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Muscidae: *Haematobia irritans irritans*

SIZE: 3/16–1/4 in.

FOOD: Blood of cattle, horses, swine, dogs, and humans

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: dark tint on wings due to micropubescence; males have dark brown to black legs and females have yellow legs.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They are known to cluster around the horns of livestock, hence their common name.

Horse Flies

#067

MOUTHPARTS: Cutting-sponging

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- pest to cattle, horses, and humans. Bites are painful and may cause allergic reactions.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Tabanidae: Tabaninae

SIZE: 3/8–15/16 in.

FOOD: plant juices, nectar, blood (females only).

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: robust and stout-bodied; huge eyes; antennae with five antennomeres, going from thick at the base to thinner at the tip.

4,300 spp. worldwide, 180+ spp. in North America, 42+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Only females bite and consume blood.

House Fly

#068

MOUTHPARTS: Sponging

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- can swarm around garbage; larvae can infest soils with high organic matter content; can spread pathogens.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Muscidae: *Musca domestica*

SIZE: ¼ –5/15 in.

FOOD: General feeders- sweet liquids, rotting fruit, feces.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: reddish eyes, thorax with four narrow black stripes, sharp upward bend in the 4th longitudinal wing vein.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Houseflies can taste with their feet, as they have chemoreceptors in their tarsi.

Mosquitoes

#092

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- transmit diseases such as West Nile, Malaria, and Dengue fever.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Culicidae

SIZE: 1/8–1/4 in.

FOOD: Plant nectar, fruit juices, blood (females only).

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: slender elongated body covered with scales; veins of the wings covered with scales; long fragile-looking legs; elongated piercing mouthparts; males have feathery antennae.

Over 3,500 spp. worldwide, Over 200 spp. in North America, 85 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Mosquitos cause over 700,000 deaths worldwide per year.

*Questions 11, 14, 33, 202, and 222 involve these insects.

Mosquito Larva**

#093

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- larvae are aquatic and a nuisance in areas of standing water; some can spread disease even as larvae.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Culicidae

SIZE: ~5/16 in.

FOOD: Algae and other small aquatic organisms.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Large head and thorax with narrow wormlike abdomen; air tubes at the end of the abdomen.

Over 3,500 spp. worldwide, over 200 spp. in North America, 85 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Mosquito larvae are known as "wrigglers" because of the way they swim.

Robber Fly

#107

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- predate on many pest species.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Asilidae

SIZE: 1/8–1 ½ in. with an average of 3/8–5/8 in.

FOOD: Other insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Stout, often hairy, large-faceted eyes, "moustache" of hair bristles.

~ 6,750 spp. worldwide, ~ 1,000 spp. in North America, 25 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Between their large compound eyes, robber flies have three ocelli.

Syrphid Flies

#134

MOUTHPARTS: Sponging

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable-larvae predate on small pest insects like aphids, adults pollinate flowers. They may be a nuisance to humans as they like to get moisture and salt from sweat.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Syrphidae

SIZE: 1/8–1/2 in.

FOOD: Soft bodied insects like mealybugs and aphids as larvae; pollen, nectar, and honeydew as adults.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Broad head about the width of the abdomen or wider, large eyes.

6,200 spp. worldwide, ~ 900 spp. in North America, 134+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Some syrphid flies mimic bees. Some can hover in midair.

Ephemeroptera

06

An Overview of the order Ephemeroptera

Ephemeroptera contains mayflies. All insects in this order have **vestigial** mouthparts and **hemimetabolous** development.

Insects in this order share a reduction of the mouthparts as adults.

Ephemeroptera comes from the Greek words “ephemera” meaning short-lived, and “ptera” meaning wing, referring to their short lifespan as adults (1–2 days).

Mayflies

#084

MOUTHPARTS: Vestigial

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- mayflies are indicator species for determining ecosystem health and water quality. They are a major food source for many animals, and they help pollinate aquatic plants.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Ephemeroptera

SIZE: ¼ –3/4 in.

FOOD: Organic matter in the water as nymphs, do not feed as adults.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: large compound eyes, short bristle-like antennae, large triangular front pair of wings with a smaller rounded hind pair.

2,000 spp. worldwide, 650 spp. in North America, ~ 93 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Mayflies are the only insects with a winged immature form, called a dun or subimago.

Hemiptera

#07

An Overview of the order Hemiptera

Hemiptera contains the “true bugs”, such as cicadas, aphids, planthoppers, assassin bugs, scale insects, and more. All insects in this order have **piercing-sucking** mouthparts and **hemimetabolous** development.

Insects in this order share beak-like mouthparts that allows them to pierce and suck on their food.

Hemiptera comes from the Greek words “hemi” meaning half, and “ptera” meaning wing. This refers to the forewings of many hemipterans that are hardened at the base and membranous at the ends, the hemelytra.

*Questions 65, 93, 124, 165, and 174 involve this order.

Aphids

#004

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- aphids feed on plant sap, causing stunted growth and deformations. They can transmit plant diseases and reproduce rapidly.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Aphidoidea

SIZE: 1/32–3/16 in.

FOOD: Plant sap.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Pear-shaped and soft bodied, one pair of cornicles (little horns) projecting from the abdomen, may or may not have wings.

5,000 spp. worldwide, 1,350 spp. in North America, 100+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Aphids consume a lot of sugar in their diet, and they excrete a sugary substance called honeydew. This sugary excretion leaves a sticky coating on leaves and attracts ants that the aphids use as bodyguards.

Assassin Bugs

#006

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- feed on a broad range of prey, usually pest animals like lygus bugs, aphids, and boll weevils.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Reduviidae

SIZE: 1/5–1 ¼ in.

FOOD: Other insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Narrow head, beady eyes, long hinged needlelike mouthparts, elongate body, long legs.

~ 7,000 spp. worldwide, 160+ spp. in North America, 78+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They get their name from their quick "assassination" of their prey.

Backswimmers

#007

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial – backswimmers help control mosquito populations by feeding on their larvae. They are also prey for other aquatic insects, fish, amphibians, and more.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Notonectidae

SIZE: ~5/8 in.

FOOD: Insects, tadpoles, small fish.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Large reddish eyes, long oar-like hind legs, oval body.

350 spp. worldwide, 32 spp. in North America, 14+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Backswimmers usually swim belly-up, and they can stay underwater for extended periods of time by trapping an air bubble against their body.

Bedbug

#009

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- bedbugs feed on blood, causing skin irritation and sometimes allergic reactions. Infestations are difficult and costly to treat.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Cimicidae: *Cimex lectularius*

SIZE: 3/16–1/4 in.

FOOD: Blood.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Long, brown, flat, oval shaped body; balloon-like and elongated if fed recently.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Bedbugs are not known to transmit diseases to humans.

*Question 137 involves this insect.

Big-Eyed Bugs

#012

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- they feed on pest species and their eggs.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Geocoridae: *Geocoris* spp.

SIZE: 1/8–1/4 in.

FOOD: Insect eggs, mites, aphids, other small invertebrates.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Large protruding eyes, oval shaped body; black, brownish, gray, or reddish bodies; short antennae slightly enlarged at the tip.

140 spp. worldwide, 25 spp. in North America, 6+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Big-eyed bugs emit an unpleasant odor when handled.

Boxelder Bug

#022

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemiptera

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest-may cause minor plant damage but are of no major economic or human health impact. They can invade homes and be a general nuisance.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Rhopalidae: *Boisea trivittata*

SIZE: ½ in.

FOOD: Boxelder tree seeds and new leaves; occasionally feed on plum and apple fruit.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Black with orange and red markings including three red stripes on prothorax.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Boxelder bugs release a foul odor when crushed.

Cicadas

#030

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable- in large numbers they may cause damage to young trees and fruit trees but are otherwise not harmful. Important food sources for birds and improve soil aeration and water infiltration.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Cicadoidea

SIZE: 1–1.5 in.

FOOD: Fluids from woody shrubs and trees.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Short antennae, two pairs of transparent membranous wings, prominent compound eyes, three ocelli forming a triangle between the compound eyes.

3,390 spp. worldwide, 190 spp. in North America, 54 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They spend most of their lives underground as nymphs. Some species live up to 17 years.

*Question 133 involves this insect.

Damsel Bugs

#037

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- they feed on a variety of pest insects.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Nabidae

SIZE: 3/8–1/2 in.

FOOD: Primarily small invertebrates, sometimes plant juices.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Many short, parallel veins at the wing tips, tibia of front legs is enlarged, long curved beaklike mouthparts, small head, bulging eyes.

Over 500 spp. worldwide, 41 spp. in North America, 13+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: If damsel bugs can't find adequate food, they will cannibalize each other.

Giant Water Bug

#057

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- they eat pest species such as mosquito larvae.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Belostomatidae: *Lethocerus americanus*

SIZE: 2–3 in.

FOOD: Tadpoles, fish, and other arthropods.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: oval-shaped, pincer-like front legs, flattened rear legs with tiny hairs.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Males protect eggs and carry them on their back.

*Question 124 involves this insect.

Lace Bugs

#074

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- Lace bugs can cause leaf discoloration and premature dropping. Repeated infestations can stunt plant growth.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Tingidae

SIZE: 1/8–1/4 in.

FOOD: Sap from trees and shrubs.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: lace-like front wings, whitish with tan markings.

1,820 spp. worldwide, 154 spp. in North America, 21+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Their life cycle takes 7–9 weeks, usually with two generations occurring in a season.

Leaf-footed Bugs

#078

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- They can cause damage to grains, nuts, fruits, and ornamental plants.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Coreidae

SIZE: ¾–1 in.

FOOD: Fruits, vegetables, nuts, ornamentals; particularly seeds.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Dark brown; hind legs with flattened leaf-like expansions on the tibia.

1,000 spp. worldwide, ~ 90 spp. in North America, 59+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They make a noisy buzzing sound when they fly.

Leafhoppers

#079

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- may injure plants and spread plant diseases.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Cicadellidae

SIZE: ~¼ in.

FOOD: Sap from vascular plants.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Often colorful; body longer than wide, wedge shaped; one or more rows of spikes extending along hind tibia.

Over 20,000 spp. worldwide, 3,000 spp. in North America, 275 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: The oldest leafhopper fossil is over 125 million years old!

Mealybugs

#085

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- high populations can reduce plant growth and cause leaf drop. Their honeydew secretions from feeding can decrease fruit quality and cause black mold to grow on plants.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Pseudococcidae

SIZE: 1/20-1/5 in.

FOOD: Plant sap.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Soft-bodied, covered in a powdery wax, often with filaments surrounding the edges of the body.

2,200 spp. worldwide, 320 spp. in North America, 12+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Depending on the species, they can lay eggs or give live birth.

Milkweed Bug

#087

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- more of a nuisance pest but may cause seed pod deformation and crowd out Monarch butterflies that also feed on milkweed.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Lygaeidae: *Oncopeltus fasciatus*

SIZE: ¾ in.

FOOD: Flower nectar, sap from milkweed seeds, scavenged foods, caterpillars, and other insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Reddish orange with a conspicuous black band across the middle and two large diamond-shaped black patches before and after.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Milkweed bugs are not palatable to predators for the same reasons Monarchs aren't- they contain the same toxins as their food.

Minute Pirate Bugs

#089

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- minute pirate bugs are beneficial as biological control. They feed on small arthropods, many of which are pest species.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Anthocoridae: *Orius* spp.

SIZE: 1/5 in.

FOOD: soft bodied insects and mites as well as pollen and plant juice.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Bulging eyes, oblong to oval body that appears somewhat flattened on top.

600 spp. worldwide, 90 spp. in North America, 3+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: In the fall when their food sources begin to die, they may bite humans.

Scales (Scale Insects)

#110

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- high populations on plants can cause damage to leaves, branch dieback, and promote mold growth.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Coccoidea

SIZE: 1/8–1/2 in.

FOOD: Tree and shrub sap.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Soft bodied, covered in wax.

~ 8,000 spp. worldwide, ~ 1,000 spp. in North America, 70+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Their waxy coating helps protect them against predators and insecticides.

*Questions 94 and 131 involve these insects.

Spittlebugs

#122

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- damage from heavy feeding on plants may cause stunted plant growth and deformity.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Aphrophoridae

SIZE: 3-27 mm.

FOOD: Plant juices, fruits, and herbs.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: two false eyes at the end of the wings.

990 spp. worldwide, 30+ spp. in North America, 10+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They produce "spittle" bubble masses to house nymphs, providing predator protection, insulation, and humidity.

*Question 59 involves these insects.

Squash Bug

#125

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- feeding from squash bugs can cause leaves to turn black and die. Feeding can also kill small fruits and cause reduced fruit quality.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Coreidae: *Anasa tristis*

SIZE: 5/8 in.

FOOD: Leaves, stems, and fruit from cucurbit plants.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: flattened, dark grey to dark brown, abdomen with alternating orange and brown stripes.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Squash bugs have one generation per year in cooler climates (North) but 2–3 per year in warmer regions (South).

*Question 165 involve this insect.

Stink Bugs

#127

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable- some species, such as the Brown Marmorated Stink Bug, are major agricultural pests that cause extensive crop damage. Other species predate upon other pest species like caterpillars and plant-feeding stink bugs.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Pentatomidae

SIZE: ~ ¾ in.

FOOD: First generation weeds, grasses, fruits, occasionally other insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Round or oval (sometimes shield shaped) bodies, antennae of five antennomeres.

5,000 spp. worldwide, 200+ spp. in North America, 111+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Stink bugs produce a foul odor than can linger on porous materials. It has been described as smelling like rotting vegetables, skunk, cilantro, or coriander.

Tarnished Plant Bug

#136

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- they can transmit plant diseases and cause leaf yellowing, reduced growth, and flower abnormalities.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Lygaeidae: *Lygus lineolaris*

SIZE: ~ ¼ in.

FOOD: Plant sap.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Oval and flattened body; greenish brown with reddish brown markings on wings; scutellum as a yellow-tipped triangle.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Females lay their eggs inside plant tissues.

Toad Bugs

#141

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- they help control populations of smaller pest insects.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Gelastocoridae

SIZE: ~ ¼ in.

FOOD: Smaller insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Bulging eyes, short antennae below the head, raptorial forelegs notably shorter than hind legs.

110 spp. worldwide, 8 spp. in North America, 2+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Toad bugs get their name from the way they leap onto their prey.

Treehoppers

#144

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- vector and spread plant diseases. Extensive feeding can cause plant damage, and their honeydew secretions can promote mold growth.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Membracidae

SIZE: ½ in.

FOOD: Sap of woody plants.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: large pronotum that extends backward to cover the abdomen and, in many species, forward to cover the head as well.

3,200 spp. worldwide, over 260 spp. in North America, ~ 27 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They have intricate pronotums that often resemble thorns, though sometimes they can have very complex and bizarre shapes.

Water Boatmen

#151

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- water boatmen are important in the diets of fish.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Corixidae

SIZE: 1/8–1/4 in.

FOOD: Plant material and algae.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Slender, oval, streamlined body; long, oarlike hind legs with fine hairs; several narrow dark parallel crosslines on back.

~ 500 spp. worldwide, ~ 125 spp. in North America, 17+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Males can produce a chirping sound with their forelegs.

Water Striders

#152

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- feed on other aquatic insects and are important food sources for birds.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Gerridae

SIZE: 1/2–3/4 in.

FOOD: Insects on the pond's surface.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Thin body, very long slender legs with tiny hairs.

Over 750 spp. worldwide, 47 spp. in North America, 13+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: The hairs on their legs are water repellent, allowing them to walk on water.

Whiteflies

#155

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest—they cause leaf yellowing and plant death at high populations. Honeydew secretions promote mold growth. Some species transmit plant diseases.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Aleyrodidae

SIZE: ~ 1/16 in.

FOOD: Plant sap.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Wings and body covered with a white waxy powder.

Over 1500 spp. worldwide, ~ 150 spp. in North America, 17+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: freshly hatched nymphs have legs, but they lose them after a few days and resemble scales until they become adults.

Hymenoptera

08

An Overview of the order Hymenoptera

Hymenoptera contains ants, bees, wasps, and sawflies. All insects in this order have **holometabolous** development.

Insects in this order share hamuli, hooks that hold the back and front wings together.

Hymenoptera comes from the Greek words “hymen” meaning membrane, and “ptera” meaning wing. This refers to their often see-through, membranous wings.

*Questions 105, 149, 164, 212, and 248 involve this order.

Bumble Bees

#024

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing-lapping

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable- bumblebees are important for plant and crop pollination. Their nests may become problematic when built in areas with lots of humans, as they can become aggressive and sting if disturbed.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Apidae *Bombus* spp.

SIZE: ~3/4–1 in.

FOOD: Pollen and nectar.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Round bodies covered in setae making them appear and feel fuzzy, they display warning coloring of yellow and black.

250 spp. worldwide, 40 spp. in North America, 9 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Bumble bees perform "buzz pollination", stimulating flowers to release pollen through their wing vibrations.

Carpenter Ants

#026

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- carpenter ants excavate wood to make their nests. Damage from nesting compromises structural integrity of homes and other wooden structures.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Formicidae: *Camponotus* spp.

SIZE: ¼–9/16 in.

FOOD: Sugary liquids and honey dew from insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Black or reddish bodies, elbowed antennae.

~ 1,000 spp. worldwide, 13+ spp. in North America, 3+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Carpenter ants only excavate wood to make nests, they don't eat it like a termite would.

Cicada Killers

#031

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- cicada killers control cicada populations and are pollinators.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Sphecidae: *Sphecius* spp.

SIZE: ~1.5 in.

FOOD: cicadas and other large insects as larvae, flower nectar and sap as adults.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Black abdomen with three yellow bands; head and thorax rust colored to dark brown; transparent reddish-brown wings.

11+ spp. worldwide, 4+ spp. in North America, 3+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: The cicada killer's venom paralyzes their prey, which they drag back to their burrows to lay their eggs on them to feed their larvae.

Honeybees

#064

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing-lapping

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- Honeybees contribute billions of dollars to crop production, pollinating a significant portion of crops.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Apidae: *Apis mellifera*

SIZE: ~ ½ in. (workers), ~ 7/8 in. (queens).

FOOD: Pollen and nectar.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Oval shaped, varying black and yellow bands on abdomen.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: 1 lb. of honey requires 2 million flower visits. Honeybees are considered livestock.

*Questions 20, 46, 125, 192, and 224 involve this insect.

Horntail Wasps

#066

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- their larvae burrow into the wood of trees and timber is occasionally harvested with the larvae of these wasps still developing inside

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Siricidae

SIZE: ½–1 ½ in.

FOOD: wood and fungus.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Large robust, spear-shaped cornus at the tail end with females having a long ovipositor under the cornus.

124 spp. worldwide, 23+ spp. in North America, 6+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Horntail wasps do not sting. What may look like a long stinger is their ovipositor, which females use to drill into wood and lay their eggs.

Ichneumon Wasps

#069

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- parasitizes pest insects.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Ichneumonidae

SIZE: Variable, average of ~ ½ in.

FOOD: Nectar, sap, and insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Slender bodied; clear wings; females with long ovipositor.

~ 40,000 spp. worldwide, 5,000 spp. in North America, 158+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Ichneumons are great hunters- their name means "tracker" or "Footprint" in Greek.

Mud-dauber Wasps

#094

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable – they can be a nuisance when they build their nests around buildings but are otherwise not harmful. They can control spiders and other pests.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Sphecidae or Crabronidae

SIZE: ¾–1 in.

FOOD: Plant nectar, honeydew, body fluids of spiders.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Thread-like waist separating the abdomen and thorax, wings often folded straight or downwards when resting, body relatively devoid of hairs.

800+ spp. worldwide, 125+ spp. in North America, 30+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Mud-daubers make small nests out of mud and live a solitary life.

Paper Wasps

#097

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable- they can be a nuisance when they build their nests around buildings but are otherwise not harmful. They are beneficial in controlling pest insects by feeding on their larvae.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Vespidae (Polistinae, Vespinae, Stenogastrinae)

SIZE: ¾–1 in.

FOOD: Sugars from nectar, garden pests such as aphids and caterpillars.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Long legs; wings often pointed upwards when resting.

~ 3,000 spp. worldwide, 22+ spp. in North America, 20+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Paper wasps build their umbrella-shaped nests by chewing wood and mixing it with saliva to make a waterproof pulpy building material.

Red Harvester Ant

#104

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – Generally not serious pests but can cause damage to crops by eating seeds.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Formicidae: *Pogonomyrmex barbatus*

SIZE: ~ 0.28 in. (workers); ~ 0.47 in. (queen).

FOOD: Seeds.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Long reddish bodies, square heads, no spines.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Red harvester ants are a favorite food source of horned lizards.

Red Imported Fire Ant

#105

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – They can cause damage to crops by feeding on seeds, seedlings, and developing fruits. They are also medically important, as their stings cause burning and blisters.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Formicidae: *Solenopsis invicta*

SIZE: ~ 0.24 in. (workers).

FOOD: Sugars, insects, seed oils.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Pedicel consists of 2 segments, polymorphic workers; antennae with ten antennomeres ending in club of two antennomeres.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Red Imported Fire Ants were brought to America on a cargo ship from South America. They were introduced in the port of Mobile, Alabama around the 1930's.

*Question 29 involves this insect.

Tarantula Hawks

#135

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable – Important in controlling tarantula populations. They are generally not aggressive, but their nests in the soil may cause disturbance to turf grass.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Pompilidae: *Pepsis* spp.

SIZE: up to 2 in.

FOOD: tarantulas as larvae, nectar and pollen as adults.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Slender somewhat iridescent steel blue bodies with orange/amber/blue-black wings.

130 spp. worldwide, 16+ spp. in North America, 9+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: The tarantula hawk's sting paralyzes their victim but keeps them alive. When their eggs hatch, the larvae burrows into the still-living tarantula to feast upon it.

Trichogramma Wasps

#145

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial – These tiny parasitic wasps parasitize the eggs of pest species and are commonly used as biological control.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Trichogrammatidae

SIZE: ~ 0.04 in.

FOOD: Insect eggs.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Very small insects, relatively short antennae, bulging eyes, tiny red ocelli on top of head.

840 spp. worldwide, 135 spp. in North America, 2+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: The larvae of the *Trichogramma* wasp grow inside the eggs of other insects.

Velvet Ants

#147

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable- they can give a painful sting if mishandled, but they pose no real threat to human, pets, or livestock.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Mutillidae

SIZE: 1/8–1 in.

FOOD: Nectar and pollen, parasitize ground nesting insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Large bodies; hairy; wingless females that resemble worker ants; males are winged.

8,000 spp. worldwide, 435 spp. in North America, 84+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Velvet ants aren't actually ants at all- they're wasps!

Lepidoptera

#09

An Overview of the order Lepidoptera

Lepidoptera contains butterflies and moths. All insects in this order have **holometabolous** development.

Adult insects in this order share scaly wings.

Lepidoptera comes from the Greek words “lepis” meaning flake or scale, and “ptera” meaning wing.

*Questions 120, 135, 179, 190, 241 involve this order.

Armyworm

#005

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – Major agricultural pest feeding on plant leaf tissue. Major crop plants affected include maize, rice, vegetables, and cotton.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Noctuidae: *Spodoptera frugiperda*

SIZE: ~ 1 in.

FOOD: Plant nectar.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Forewings with irregular pattern of brown, black and grey; hindwings white.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Caterpillars feed in groups.

Bagworms**

#008

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – caterpillars eat leaves and can defoliate trees and shrubs.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Psychidae

SIZE: 1–2 in.

FOOD: plant leaves, commonly conifers.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Cone-shaped larval case made of leaves and plant debris.

~ 1,000 spp. worldwide, ~ 30 spp. in North America, 7 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Adult females are wingless and remain in their bags their whole lives.

Beet Armyworm**

#011

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – Caterpillars feed on the foliage of a wide variety of crops and can cause severe crop loss when occurring in large numbers.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Noctuidae: *Spodoptera exigua*

SIZE: ~ 1 ¼ in.

FOOD: Flowers, buds, fruit, foliage.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Green back with a pink or yellow underside and white stripes that run along the sides, dark spots or broken lines running along the back.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Females will adhere groups of leaves together with webbing, making a structure that helps protect against insecticides.

Black Witch Moth

#015

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable – not considered an agricultural pest but also not a major beneficial insect.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Erebididae: *Ascalapha odorata*

SIZE: Wingspan of up to 7 in.

FOOD: Woody plants.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Dark brown with iridescent pink and purple; females usually have a distinct white bar across their wings.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Because of their large wingspan, people claim they resemble bats when they fly.

Bollworm

#019

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – adults do not cause extensive damage, but larvae cause extensive damage to crops by burrowing in and feeding on fruits and flowers.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Noctuidae: *Helicoverpa armigera*

SIZE: 5/8 in. with a wingspan ~ 1 ½ in.

FOOD: Adult moths do not eat.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Cream-colored, stout-bodied, broad across the thorax then tapering.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Eggs are laid in plant canopies.

Bollworm**

#020

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – Larvae cause extensive damage to crops by burrowing in and feeding on fruits and flowers.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Noctuidae: *Helicoverpa armigera*

SIZE: Up to 2 in.

FOOD: Over 180 plant species including corn, cotton, grains, soybeans, peppers, and tomatoes.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Almost black in color fading into lighter colors as they age with longitudinal paler bands.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Eggs are laid in plant canopies.

Cabbage Looper**

#025

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – Common garden pests that eat cruciferous plants like cabbage, broccoli, and Brussel sprouts.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Noctuidae: *Trichoplusia ni*

SIZE: ~ 2 in.

FOOD: Vegetables, flower crops, field crops.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Smooth, greenish with thin white lines on its back and sides.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They get their names from the looping shape they make when moving.

Fall Webworm**

#049

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – feeds on leaves, leading to plant stress and loss of leaves. Their hairs can cause skin irritation if handled.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Erebidae: *Hyphantria cunea*

SIZE: 1 ½ in.

FOOD: Leaves of woody plants.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Yellowish or tawny with a dark stripe down the back and rows of distinctive black and orange-yellow tubercles on each side, covered by long, fine, light-colored hairs.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: The larvae create a characteristic webbed nest where temperatures vary between 104–122 degrees F. Adults rarely if ever lay eggs on the same tree year after year.

Gray Hairstreak

#058

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – Their larvae cause damage to bean pods and cotton bolls.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Lycaenidae: *Strymon melinus*

SIZE: Wingspan ~ 1.26 in.

FOOD: Nectar.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Dark gray, hindwing with 2 short tails, ventral hindwing light gray with relatively smooth black and white postmedian line (often including orange) and red-capped black spots near tails.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: The larvae can change color depending on the flower they're eating.

Indian Meal Moth

#070

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – Larvae feed on and infest stored household items like grains and cereals. Adults are a nuisance around the house but not harmful.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Pyralidae: *Plodia interpunctella*

SIZE: Wingspan 0.79 in.

FOOD: Grains, nuts, cereals, dried foods as larvae; typically, do not feed as adults but occasionally feed on fruit juices and other sugary substances.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Reddish brown with a copper luster in the posterior two thirds but whitish gray on the anterior third.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Larvae produce silk.

Luna Moth

#082

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial – Though they're not pollinators, luna moths serve as important food sources for predators.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Saturniidae: *Actias luna*

SIZE: Wingspan 3–4.25 in.

FOOD: Foliage as larvae; adults do not feed.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Pale green color each with a transparent eye spot and edged with pinkish/yellowish margins.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Adults don't have a digestive system, and they only live about a week.

Monarch Butterfly

#091

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial – important as pollinators. Can pollinate wide areas due to their migration.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Nymphalidae: *Danaus plexippus*

SIZE: Wingspan ~ 4 in.

FOOD: Milkweed as larvae, flower nectar as adults.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Bright orange-red wings featuring black veins and white spots along the edges; males have black dots along the veins of their wings.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Adults live 4–5 weeks unless they are the overwintering generation. Their migration can be over 3,000 miles.

*Questions 195 and 217 involve this insect.

Painted Lady

#096

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial - they are generalist feeders, pollinating a variety of plants.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Nymphalidae: *Vanessa cardui*

SIZE: Wingspan 2–2 ¾ in.

FOOD: Plant nectar.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Orange and brown patterned wings with white spots near the tips of the forewings.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They are the world's most widely distributed butterfly, found throughout Europe, Asia, Africa, North America, and Central America.

Queen Butterfly

#101

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial – Provides aesthetic value but no major benefits to humans.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Nymphalidae: *Danaus gilippus*

SIZE: Wingspan 3.1–3.3 in.

FOOD: Primarily nectar, also rotting fruit, sweat, and dung.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Orange-brown color with white spots and black borders.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Similar to the Monarch, queen butterfly caterpillars also feed on milkweed. The toxins in milkweed make them unpalatable to predators, and these toxins stay with them throughout metamorphosis.

Red Admiral

#102

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial – Red admirals pollinate flowers.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Nymphalidae: *Vanessa atalanta*

SIZE: Wingspan 1 ¾–3 in.

FOOD: Flower nectar, tree sap, dung.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Black background with striking orange to red colored stripes creating marginal bands on the fore and hind wings, the forewings also have white spots at the apex.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Males are territorial and will chase other males away from their roosting spots.

Skipper Butterflies

#116

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable – Larvae can occasionally be damaging to bermudagrass hay fields, but adults are pollinators.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: HesperIIDae

SIZE: ~ 1.38 in.

FOOD: nectar, occasionally mud for minerals.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: bodies are hairy and large in proportion to their wings, clubbed antennae ending in a slender hooked tip.

3,500 spp. worldwide, 275 spp. in North America, 195+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Despite their small size, they can fly up to 20 MPH.

Southwestern Corn Borer**

#119

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – Major pest of corn, causing millions of dollars in crop loss annually.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Crambidae: *Diatraea grandiosella*

SIZE: ~ 1 in.

FOOD: Corn ear and leaf tissues.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Reddish color until 2nd or 3rd instar then off-white coloration and black spots.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Egg masses usually only consist of 2–6 eggs. Eggs are white when laid but later develop red stripes.

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Sphinx Moths

#120

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable – caterpillars can be destructive garden pests to plants in the Solanaceae family, but adults are pollinators.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Sphingidae

SIZE: Wingspan up to 5 in.

FOOD: Nectar of tubular, usually yellow or white flowers.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Large heavy bodied with a long, pointed abdomen, forewings generally long and pointed although some species have angled or irregular margins.

14,500 spp. worldwide, 115 spp. in North America, 63+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They are also known as hummingbird hawk-moths; when they're hovering to feed and pollinate, they are almost indistinguishable from hummingbirds!

Sulphur Butterflies

#131

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – Larvae of some species (*Pieris rapae*) are pests of Cruciferous vegetables. Other species are harmless and pollinate flowers.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Pieridae: Coliadinae

SIZE: Wingspan 2–3 in.

FOOD: Flower nectar such as geraniums, cardinal flowers, and hibiscus.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Colors range from orange to white.

~ 1,000 spp. worldwide, 71+ spp. in North America, 21+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They are great at finding flowers to camouflage on, often choosing ones that closely match their wing color.

Swallowtail Butterflies

#132

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial – Swallowtails are effective pollinators.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Papilionidae

SIZE: Wingspan 2.5–6.4 in.

FOOD: Nectar; occasionally mud and manure.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Tail-like extensions of the hindwings however there are also many tailless species, every color under the sun.

560 spp. worldwide, ~ 30 spp. in North America, 4 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: The eastern giant swallowtail, *Papilio cresphontes*, is the largest butterfly in the U.S.

Tiger Moth

#140

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable – Caterpillars feed on leaves and may cause issues when occurring in high numbers. Adults are not pollinators but may be important food sources for predators.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Erebidae: Arctiinae

SIZE: Wingspan ~ 3 in.

FOOD: Nectar.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Dark wings with red or orange spots and white stripes sometimes displayed in striking geometric patterns.

11,000 spp. worldwide, 260 spp. in North America, ~ 125 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Some species have an auditory organ on their abdomen to help them detect and avoid bats at night, and they produce an ultrasonic clicking sound to confuse bats.

Tobacco Hornworm**

#142

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – Tobacco hornworms have a voracious appetite and are a common garden pest of plants in the Solanaceae family.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Sphingidae: *Manduca sexta*

SIZE: Up to 4 in.

FOOD: Plants in the nightshade family (Solanaceae).

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Whitish diagonal lines on the body and a horn at the end of the abdomen.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: These caterpillars can emit a short clicking sound from their mandibles when being attacked.

Viceroy Butterfly

#148

MOUTHPARTS: Siphoning

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial – They pollinate wildflowers

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Nymphalidae: *Limenitis archippus*

SIZE: Wingspan 2 ½ in.

FOOD: Nectar of Asteraceae flowers, dung, carrion, fungi.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Dark orange with black veins, a row of white spots along the edge its wings, black stripe that crosses the bottom of its back wings.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: It was once believed that Viceroy's mimic Monarchs because they could not produce their own toxins. We now know this isn't the case- they sequester salicylic acid from their host plants, giving them a bitter taste, similar to how Monarchs consume milkweed and sequester its toxins.

Mantodea

#10

An Overview of the order Mantodea

Mantodea contains mantises. All insects in this order have **chewing** mouthparts and **hemimetabolous** development.

Insects in this order share a triangular head and raptorial front legs.

Mantodea comes from the Greek words “mantis” meaning prophet, and “eidos” meaning type, referring to their “praying” front legs.

*Questions 37 and 98 involve this order.

Praying Mantis

#099

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- they are beneficial forms of natural pest control in gardens.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Mantodea

SIZE: ½–7+ in.

FOOD: Insects and other small animals.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Long, narrow body; triangular head; raptorial front legs with sharp spines.

2,500 spp. worldwide, 28 spp. in North America, ~ 8 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Mantises are the only invertebrate known to be able to see in 3D!

Mecoptera

#11

An Overview of the Order Mecoptera

Mecoptera contains scorpionflies. All insects in this order have **chewing** mouthparts and **holometabolous** development.

Insects in this order share narrowly extended heads (with rostrum) and males have long upturned genitalia resembling a scorpion's tail.

Mecoptera comes from the Greek words “meco” meaning long, and “ptera” meaning wing, referring to their long, similar-sized fore and hind wings.

*Question 66 involves this order.

Scorpion flies

#113

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- they are predators, aiding in pest control, or scavengers, assisting in environmental clean-up.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Mecoptera

SIZE: ¼–½ in.

FOOD: Decaying organic matter, dead insects, soil dwelling insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Red, orange, or yellow, and black body; head with long beaklike projection; dark patches on wings; males with long scorpion tail-like genitalia.

605 spp. worldwide, over 60 spp. in North America, 1+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Males use their tail-like appendage for courtship displays.

*Question 66 involves these insects.

Megaloptera

#12

An Overview of the Order Megaloptera

Megaloptera contains alderflies, dobsonflies, and fishflies. All insects in this order have **chewing** mouthparts and **holometabolous** development.

Adults in this order share large, intricately veiny wings.

Megaloptera comes from the Greek words “megalo” meaning large, and “ptera” meaning wings, referring to their large wings.

Dobsonflies

#044

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- they play important roles as predators in river food webs and are food sources for larger predators.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Corydalidae: Corydalinae

SIZE: Wingspan up to or greater than 6 in.

FOOD: Typically do not feed as adults, but adult females observed to occasionally feed on nectar.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Brown-gray color; large wings that cover most of the body, and typically with light spots; curved mandibles (long in males, short in females); long antennae.

~ 60 spp. worldwide, 16+ spp. in North America, 3+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Dobsonflies are one of the largest aquatic insects in North America.

*Question 122 involves these insects.

Hellgrammite**

#063

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- they play important roles as predators in river food webs and are food sources for larger predators.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Corydalidae: Corydalinae

SIZE: 2–3 in.

FOOD: Stream dwelling invertebrates- arthropods, worms, mollusks.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Flattened, segmented, caterpillar-like body, usually dark brown, tan, or black; wide head with large mandibles; thick gill filaments on abdomen.

~ 60 spp. worldwide, 16+ spp. in North America, 3+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: This is the larval form of dobsonflies. They're picky about their habitats, primarily inhabiting only the swiftest moving streams.

*Question 122 involves these insects

Neuroptera

#013

An Overview of the Order Neuroptera

Neuroptera contains antlions, lacewings, mantidflies, owlflies, and other minor groups. All insects in this order have **chewing** mouthparts and **holometabolous** development.

Insects in this order share membranous wings with intricate wing venation.

Neuroptera comes from the Greek words “neuron” meaning sinew or nerve, and “ptera” meaning wing. This refers to the extensive venation on their wings that looks like nerves.

*Question 155 involves this order.

Antlions

#002

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- larvae help control ant populations and adults are pollinators.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Myrmeleontidae

SIZE: Wingspan up to 3 ½ in.

FOOD: Nectar and pollen as adults.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Elongated body; four similarly sized, intricately veined mottled wings; clubbed antennae.

~ 2,000 spp. worldwide, ~ 1,000 spp. in North America, 43+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They get their names from their larval stage that preys on ants.

*Question 155 involves these insects.

Antlion Larva**

#003

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- larvae help control ant populations and adults are pollinators.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Myrmeleontidae

SIZE: ~ 1/2 in.

FOOD: Ants and other small insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Robust fusiform body, very plump abdomen, three pairs of walking legs, the prothorax forms a mobile “neck” for the large square flattened head which bears a pair of large, sickle-shaped mandibles with several sharp projections.

~ 2,000 spp. worldwide, ~ 1,000 spp. in North America, 43+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Antlion larvae make sand funnels to catch their food- small insects slip on the sand and tumble into the antlion’s mandibles.

Green Lacewing

#059

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- larvae are efficient predators of aphids and other small soft-bodied pests; adults are pollinators.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Chrysopidae

SIZE: 1/2–7/8 in.

FOOD: Honeydew, nectar, and pollen as adults.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Long netlike wings; slender pale green bodies; golden eyes.

Over 1,300 spp. worldwide, 85 spp. in North America, 15 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Green lacewings have a hearing organ at the base of their front wings.

Lacewing Larva**

#075

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- larvae are efficient predators of aphids and other small soft-bodied pests; adults are pollinators.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Chrysopidae

SIZE: < ½ in.

FOOD: Soft-bodied insects and insect eggs.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Elongated, flattened, segmented bodies; sickle-shaped mandibles.

Over 1,300 spp. worldwide, 85 spp. in North America, 15 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Similar to ladybird beetle larvae, some people claim they resemble tiny alligators.

Mantidflies

#083

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- Both adults and larvae are beneficial in pest control.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Mantispidae

SIZE: 7/8–1 3/8 in.

FOOD: Small insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Similar in appearance to a praying mantis; intricately veined wings, raptorial forelegs.

~ 400 spp. worldwide, 13 spp. in North America, 10 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Their larval state parasitizes spiders.

Odonata

#14

An Overview of the Order Odonata

Odonata contains dragonflies and damselflies. All insects in this order have **chewing** mouthparts, **hemimetabolous** development, and are **beneficial**.

Adults in this order have large eyes and four equal-sized veiny wings, and nymphs have prehensile mouthparts.

Odonata comes from the Greek word “odonto”, meaning tooth, referring to their strong mandibles.

Damselflies

#038

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial – They predate on a wide variety of insects, aiding in controlling pest populations.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Zygoptera

SIZE: 1–1 ½ in.

FOOD: Flying insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Very slender, elongated abdomen, delicate bodies, wings typically held together over the body, eyes on separate ends of the head with a "hammerhead" shape.

Over 5,000 spp. worldwide, 434 spp. in North America, 70 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Though they're great fliers and even better hunters, damselflies are unable to walk on flat surfaces, though they can land and perch on plant stems.

Damselfly Nymphs

#039

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial – Important predators of mosquitoes and other insects and important food sources for fish and other aquatic organisms.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Zygoptera

SIZE: up to 2 ½ in.

FOOD: Small aquatic animals.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Slender, thin legs, large eyes, three gills in a "tail" formation at the end of the abdomen.

Over 5,000 spp. worldwide, 434 spp. in North America, 70 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: some species spend up to 5 years as a nymph.

Dragonflies

#045

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial – They are one of the most efficient predators in the Animal kingdom, making them great for pest control. Some species are valuable indicators for ecosystem health.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Anisoptera

SIZE: Wingspan up to 6 in.

FOOD: Other insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Large compound eyes that meet at the top of the head, strong transparent wings, elongated and robust bodies.

Over 5,000 spp. worldwide, 483+ spp. in North America, 162+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Prehistoric dragonflies had a wingspan of up to two feet, and though they're not nearly as big anymore, Dragonflies have been around for 300 million years.

Dragonfly Nymphs

#046

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial - Important predator of mosquitoes and other insects, and important food sources for fish and other aquatic organisms.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Anisoptera

SIZE: ½–2 ½ in.

FOOD: Small aquatic animals.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: large eyes, typically large and robust bodies without long projections at the end of the abdomen.

Over 5,000 spp. worldwide, 483+ spp. in North America, 162+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They can remain a nymph up to four years.

Orthoptera

#15

An Overview of the Order Orthoptera

Orthoptera contains crickets, katydids, grasshoppers, and wetas. All insects in this order have **chewing** mouthparts and **hemimetabolous** development.

Insects in this order have saltatorial back legs, used for jumping.

Orthoptera comes from the Greek words “orthos” meaning straight and “ptera” meaning wing, referring to the parallel alignment of their front wings.

*Questions 96, 98, 100, 188 and 226 involve this order.

Field Crickets

#050

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- field crickets will feed on almost anything, so they can sometimes damage crops like alfalfa and strawberries.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Gryllidae

SIZE: 1/8–2 in.

FOOD: Plant matter, flies, grasshopper eggs, pupae of Lepidoptera.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Large hind legs, most have well-developed wings, long slender antennae.

1,100 spp. worldwide, 112+ spp. in North America, 25+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Only the males chirp.

Jerusalem Crickets

#072

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable- they are an important part of the food chain and assist in environmental cleaning by eating organic decaying matter. They may cause damage to turf grass and roots of crops.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Stenopelmatini

SIZE: 2–3 in.

FOOD: Other insects, roots, decaying plant material, carrion.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Stout-bodied; large, rounded, shiny heads with strong mandibles and small eyes; plump abdomens with hunched backs; wingless; stout legs adapted for digging.

~ 100 spp. worldwide, 14 spp. in North America, 2+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Their powerful mandibles can easily cut through fabric and even thin plastic.

Long-horned Grasshoppers

#080

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable- they are an important food source for bug eating animals, but they can cause damage to crops.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Tettigoniidae

SIZE: 2–5 in.

FOOD: Leaves, flowers, seeds, bark; some species may exhibit predatory behavior and eat other insects and even small vertebrates.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Long, threadlike antennae; long saltatorial back legs; females with long ovipositor.

Over 6,000 spp. worldwide, 255 spp. in North America, ~ 70 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Also known as katydids. They have hearing organs on their front legs!

Mole Crickets

#090

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- heir tunneling habits and diet of roots can damage turf grass and plants.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Gryllotalpidae

SIZE: 7/8–2 in.

FOOD: Plant material such as roots and tubers, occasionally other insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Fossorial forelegs modified for digging; cylindrical body with a velvety coat of hairlike setae; pointed head.

Over 100 spp. worldwide, 7 spp. in North America, 3 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Mole crickets have an exceptionally loud chirp that can be heard from over half a mile away.

*Questions 35 and 110 involve these insects.

Short-horned Grasshoppers

#114

MOUThPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- their primarily plant-based diet can cause extensive harm to crops when present in large enough numbers.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Acrididae

SIZE: ¼–4 in.

FOOD: Leaves, flowers, stems, seeds, occasionally scavenge dead insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Large, well developed saltatorial hind legs for jumping; short antennae usually ½ the length of the body.

8,000 spp. worldwide, 611 spp. in North America, 150 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Many males produce sound by rubbing their legs against their wings

Tree Crickets

#143

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable- they eat soft bodied pest insects like aphids and scales, but egg laying can harm woody ornamental trees.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Oecanthidae: Oecanthinae

SIZE: ¼–4 in.

FOOD: Soft bodied insects and plant parts.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Long slender shape; pale colors; forewings of males broad and flat whereas wing of females are long, narrow, and wrapped closely to the body.

~ 300 spp. worldwide, ~ 20 spp. in North America, 15+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Tree crickets are good jumpers, leaping with quick speed and accuracy.

Phasmatodea

16

An Overview of the Order Phasmatodea

Phasmatodea contains stick insects and leaf insects. All insects in this order have **chewing** mouthparts and **hemimetabolous** development.

Insects in this order have long stick-like bodies.

Phasmatodea comes from the Greek word “phasm” meaning phantom, referring to their cryptic appearance.

*Questions 85, 96, and 140 involve this order.

Walkingsticks

#150

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable – Can damage foliage of trees and crops when in high enough numbers, but this rarely happens. They are harmless to humans and serve as a food source to bats, birds, reptiles, and other insect eating animals.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Phasmatodea

SIZE: ½ to over 12 in.

FOOD: Leaves of trees and shrubs.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Long and narrow bodies, often wingless but some have short leathery front wings or large colorful hind wings folded over the abdomen, long legs.

3,630 spp. worldwide, 29 spp. in North America, 14 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Some can reproduce asexually.

*Question 140 involves these insects.

Phthiraptera

17

An Overview of the order Phthiraptera

Phthiraptera contains biting and sucking lice. All insects in this order have **hemimetabolous** development and are all considered **pests**.

Insects in this order are small, wingless, blind, and have dorsoventrally flattened bodies.

Phthiraptera comes from the Greek words “phthir” meaning lice, and “aptera” meaning wingless.

*Question 159 involves this order.

Biting Louse

#013

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – cause skin irritation to hosts.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Mallophaga

SIZE: ~ 3/16 in.

FOOD: Skin, feathers, and other skin products of birds and occasionally mammals.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Flattened, somewhat oval bodies; head wider than thorax; visible claws at the end of legs.

Over 2,650 spp. worldwide, 90+ spp. in North America, 7+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: These ectoparasites are rarely detrimental to hosts, but they can cause skin irritation.

Sucking Louse

#130

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – infest humans and other mammals wherever hygienic practices are not maintained.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Anoplura

SIZE: ~ 3/16 in.

FOOD: Blood.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Fusiform body, pointed, narrow head.

Over 550 spp. worldwide, 70 spp. in North America, 24+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They are the only blood-feeding ectoparasites to live permanently on the host throughout all stages of development.

*Question 159 involves these insects.

Plecoptera

18

An Overview of the order Plecoptera

Plecoptera contains stoneflies. All insects in this order have **chewing** mouthparts and **hemimetabolous** development.

Nymphs of insects in this order have two long filaments (cerci) at the end of their abdomen and occupy cool, clean waters.

Plecoptera comes from the Greek work "pleco" meaning folded and "ptera" meaning wing, referring to how their hind wings fold under their front wings.

Stoneflies

#128

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial – Aid in the redistribution of nutrients and are indicators of good-quality waters.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Plecoptera

SIZE: ¼– 2 ½ in.

FOOD: Algae (as nymphs), lichens, nectar, pollens (as adults).

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Long antennae, two pairs of membranous wings.

3,400 spp. worldwide, 670 spp. in North America, 20 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They remain in their nymphal stage for anywhere from 6 months to 3 years, and adults live 1–4 weeks.

Stonefly larva**

#129

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial – feed on fly larvae.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Plecoptera

SIZE: 5/8–1 ¼ in.

FOOD: Dead vegetation, algae, other aquatic invertebrates.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Two long filaments at the end of the abdomen, may have external gills.

3,400 spp. worldwide, 670 spp. in North America, 20 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: One of the most pollution sensitive insects and only live in running water.

Psocoptera

#19

An Overview of the order Psocoptera

Psocoptera contains booklice. All insects in this order have **chewing** mouthparts, **ametabolous** development, and are considered **pests**.

Insects in this order have long, segmented antennae and some have well-developed wings.

Psocoptera comes from the Greek words “psokos” meaning rubbed or gnawed and “ptera” meaning wing. The name prefix refers to their feeding method, while the suffix indicates wing presence.

Book louse

#021

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – can contaminate household food with their carcasses and excrement.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Psocoptera

SIZE: ~3/16 in.

FOOD: Grains, wallpaper, glue, book binding, lichens, algae, dead plant, and insect material.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Soft-bodied; rounded broad head with bulging clypeus; long slender antennae.

5,000 spp. worldwide, Over 240 spp. in North America, 3+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They molt six times before adulthood.

Siphonaptera

#20

An Overview of the order Siphonaptera

Siphonaptera contains fleas. All insects in this order have **piercing-sucking** mouthparts, **holometabolous** development, and are **pests**.

Insects in this order are small, laterally flattened, wingless, and have modified back legs for jumping.

Siphonaptera comes from the Greek words “siphon” meaning tube or pipe and “aptera” meaning wingless, referring to fleas as being “wingless tubes” that suck blood.

Fleas

#052

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Holometabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – transmit germs that cause disease primarily through feeding on sick hosts or through fecal contamination.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Siphonaptera

SIZE: 1/16–1/8 in.

FOOD: Blood of mammals and birds.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Strong tarsal claws; backward pointing hairs and bristles.

2,500 spp. worldwide, 325 spp. in North America, 6+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They can jump up to a foot in the air, around 150 times their height. When mounted in microscope slides, always posed in lateral view.

*Questions 79 and 184 involve these insects.

Thysanoptera

21

An Overview of the order Thysanoptera

Thysanoptera contains thrips. All insects in this order have **rasping-sucking** mouthparts, **hemimetabolous** development, and are of **variable** significance to humans.

Insects in this order are wingless or have rod-like wings with hairy fringe.

Thysanoptera comes from the Greek words “thysanos” meaning fringe and “ptera” meaning wing, referring to their wing structure.

*Questions 82 and 132 involve this order.

Thrips

#138

MOUTHPARTS: Rasping-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Hemimetabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable – some can be predators of mites and other insects, but some plant feeders can cause distorted and discolored flowers and buds.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Thysanoptera

SIZE: 1/16–1/8 in.

FOOD: Plant juices, pollen, and decaying vegetation.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: cigar-shaped body plan, elongated; fringed wings.

6,300 spp. worldwide, 1,000 spp. in North America, 23+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They have asymmetrical mouthparts, with one mandible longer than the other.

*Question 242 involves these insects.

Thysanura

22

An Overview of the order Thysanura

Thysanura contains silverfish and firebrats. All insects in this order have **chewing** mouthparts, **ametabolous** development, and are considered **pests**.

Insects in this order have three thread-like “tails” on their last abdominal segment (caudal filaments).

Thysanura comes from the Greek words “thysanos” meaning fringe or bristle and “oura” meaning tail, referring to their long caudal filaments.

*Questions 7 and 97 involve this order.

Silverfish

#115

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – infest items such as wallpaper, books, and envelopes.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Zygentoma

SIZE: ¼–1 ¼ in.

FOOD: Paper, glue, fabric, starches and protein-rich items like grains, cereals, and pet food.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Wingless; long antennae; body is wide at the head and tapers down to the posterior end where three long appendages with bristles appear.

550 spp. worldwide, 19 spp. in North America, 4 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They live 3–6 years, and females can lay 2–20 eggs everyday for the rest of her life upon reaching adulthood.

*Question 7 involves these insects.

Non-insects

23

An Overview of the Non-Insects of the List

The animals in this group are not insects, but they are all in the phylum Arthropoda.

The arthropods included all have **ametabolous** development.

Arachnids

The animals in this group have four pairs of legs, lack antennae and wings, and their bodies are divided in two main sections: cephalothorax and abdomen.

This group includes scorpions, spiders, ticks, mites, harvestmen, vinegaroons, and others.

Black Widow Spider

#014

MOUTHPARTS: N/A

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – they have medically significant venom.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Arachnida: Araneae: Theridiidae: *Latrodectus* spp.

SIZE: 1/8–3/8 in. body not including legs.

FOOD: Insects, primarily Hymenoptera and Hemiptera.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Females shiny black with red-orange hourglass marking on ventral side of the abdomen; males brown or gray with small red spots.

6 spp. worldwide, 3 spp. in North America, 3 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Black widow spiderlings are cannibalistic.

Brown Recluse Spider

#023

MOUTHPARTS: N/A

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest-medically significant venom.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Arachnida: Araneae:
Sicariidae: *Loxosceles reclusa*

SIZE: 1/8–3/8 in. body not including legs.

FOOD: Insects such as crickets, cockroaches,
moths, and flies.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Three pairs of eyes;
violin shaped marking on cephalothorax.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in
Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They prefer to feed on insects
that are already dead.

Crab Spiders

#035

MOUTHPARTS: N/A

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial – they eat lots of pest insects.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Arachnida: Araneae: Thomisidae

SIZE: ½–1 in.

FOOD: Insects such as flies and bees, as well as other spiders.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Short, wide, flat bodies; first two pairs of legs are larger than the third and fourth pairs of legs.

2,100 spp. worldwide, ~ 200 spp. in North America, ~ 20 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They tend to walk sideways or backwards, only using their back two sets of legs.

Garden Spider

#055

MOUTHPARTS: N/A

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial- they eat unwanted insects in gardens.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Arachnida: Araneae:
Araneidae: *Argiope aurantia*

SIZE: 3/8–3/4 in. (males); 3/4–1 3/16 in. (females),
not including legs.

FOOD: Insects such as flies, grasshoppers, aphids,
mosquitos, and wasps.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Males brown, females
black with bright yellow patches.

1 sp. worldwide, 1 sp. in North America, 1 sp. in
Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Their webs can be up to 2 ft. in
diameter.

Hard Ticks

#061

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest-damage host by drawing large amounts of blood and secreting neurotoxins that sometimes produce paralysis, death, or disease.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Arachnida: Ixodida: Ixodidae

SIZE: 1/4–3/8 in.

FOOD: Blood.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: With plate behind their head called a scutum, mouthparts visible when viewed from above.

700+ spp. worldwide, 47+ spp. in North America, 12+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Ticks don't have the best vision, but they can sense their prey through vibrations, body odor, and body heat.

*Question 130 involves these invertebrates.

Harvestmen

#062

MOUTHPARTS: N/A

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable – feed on all sorts of arthropods, both pest and beneficial.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Arachnida: Opiliones

SIZE: ~5/16–1/2 in. not including legs.

FOOD: Decaying plant material, fungi, dead insects, sometimes hunt small insects.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Two eyes; oval, often segmented abdomen; second pair of legs usually the longest.

Over 6,600 spp. worldwide, 60+ spp. in North America, 18 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: The oldest record of harvestmen dates to the Devonian age- over 400 million years old.

Jumping Spiders

#073

MOUTHPARTS: N/A

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial – help with insect population control

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Arachnida: Araneae: Salticidae

SIZE: 1/8–7/8 in. not including legs.

FOOD: Small arthropods like flies, mosquitoes, mites, and small beetles.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Large anterior median eyes; fuzzy appearance with a dense covering of scales or hairs.

5,800 spp. worldwide, 350 spp. in North America, 135+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They can jump up to 50 times their body length.

Scorpions

#112

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – migrate in numbers and quickly invade areas when food is abundant, extremely painful sting with some having medically significant venom

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Arachnida: Scorpiones

SIZE: 1/16–1 in. without the tail.

FOOD: Insects, arachnids, pillbugs, snails, small vertebrates like lizards.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: First pair of legs ending with grasping pinchers; narrow segmented tail often carried in a forward curve over the back and ending with a stinger.

2,000 spp. worldwide, 50 spp. in North America, ~ 18 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Scorpions glow under UV light!

*Question 197 involves these invertebrates.

Soft Ticks

#117

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest- vectors of various diseases

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Arachnida: Ixodida: Argasidae

SIZE: 3/8–9/16 in.

FOOD: Blood.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Without plate behind their head; mouthparts not visible from above.

183 spp. worldwide, 8+ spp. in North America, 4+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Some species of soft tick can live for over 10 years!

Spider Mites

#121

MOUTHPARTS: Piercing-sucking

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Pest – injure plants through feeding, bruise cells with their mouthparts and ingest sap.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Arachnida: Trombidiformes: Tetranychidae

SIZE: ~ 0.04 in.

FOOD: Plant sap, chlorophyll, plant tissue.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Red, brown, yellow, or green coloration; body rounded or oval.

1,250+ spp. worldwide, 21+ spp. in North America, 7+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They get their name from the web-like structure they place around their eggs.

Vinegaroons

#149

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable – can pinch and spray a mist from scent glands at base of tail when disturbed, but they are effective predators of pests.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Arachnida: Uropygi

SIZE: 1–3.3 in.

FOOD: Slugs, worms, small insects such as crickets, termites, and cockroaches.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Pincher-like pedipalps; first pair of legs is the longest; long thin tail.

Under 100 spp. worldwide, 3 spp. in North America, 1 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: They get their name from the vinegar-like compound they spray out of their abdomen in self defense.

Myriapods

The animals in this group have many pairs of legs, one pair of antennae, simple eyes, and lack wings. Their bodies are divided in two main sections: head and trunk.

This group includes millipedes and centipedes.

Centipedes

#029

MOUTHPARTS: N/A

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable – they can control insect populations as well as improve soil fertility by breaking down organic matter in the soil. However, they are venomous.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Myriapoda: Chilopoda

SIZE: 3/8–6 in.

FOOD: Insects and other small animals.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Long, multisegmented, flattened body with 15–181 segments; one pair of legs per segment (except the last one); number of segments is always an odd number.

3,000 spp. worldwide, 300 spp. in North America, ~ 30 spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Centipedes can regrow their legs!

Question 147 involves these invertebrates.

Millipede

#088

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Beneficial – help return nutrients back into the soil.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Myriapoda: Diplopoda

SIZE: 1–12 in.

FOOD: Decaying organic matter such as wood, leaves, and fruit.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Cylindrical or flattened body with around 20 segments; two pairs of legs per segment.

12,000+ spp. worldwide, 500 spp. in North America, 51+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Most millipedes only have six body segments and three pairs of legs when they hatch. As they grow and molt, they gain new legs and body segments.

Crustaceans

The animals in this group have five pairs of legs, two pairs of antennae, compound eyes, and lack wings. Their bodies are divided in two main sections: cephalothorax and abdomen; the abdomen also has legs.

This group includes primarily marine arthropods like crabs and lobsters, but also pillbugs, which are terrestrial.

Pillbugs

#098

MOUTHPARTS: Chewing

METAMORPHOSIS: Ametabolous

SIGNIFICANCE: Variable – recycle decaying matter back into the environment and stimulate soil bacteria. Occasionally they feed on new plant material and come indoors, which can be a nuisance.

HIGHER TAXONOMY: Crustacea: Malacostraca: Isopoda: Armadillidiidae

SIZE: ¼-¾ in.

FOOD: Decaying plant matter, algae, moss, wood.

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERS: Seven pairs of legs; small head; six small abdominal segments; seven relatively large thoracic segments each with one pair of legs.

10,000 spp. worldwide, 3+ spp. in North America, 2+ spp. in Texas.

OTHER FUN FACTS: Females carry their eggs in a pouch. These are the only fully terrestrial crustaceans.

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